

WORKFORCE DIVERSITY: A KEY TO IMPROVE PRODUCTIVITY AT PREETHI HOSPITAL

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Abstract:

This paper describes about the employee’s workforce diversity in terms of culture, age, gender, ethnicity, racial background and training in terms of its need, development and effectiveness. This study reveals when the organization has a good training for practicing workforce diversity, employees will enjoy all the positive benefits such as motivation, knowledge and skill transfer, creativity and better decision making. Hence employees are enhances the organization’s growth. If workforce diversity and training is not handled correctly, the diverse workforce will badly effect organization growth. This research also aims to see the “how workforce diversity (cultural, age, gender, ethnicity), employee training and development influences on employee’s performance in their workplace”, in which Workforce Diversity, Training and Development consider as independent whereas dependent variable „Employee Performance“. This research investigates the relationship between work force diversity (cultural, age, gender, and ethnicity), training development and employee performance in the IT Companies and also how work force diversity, training and development influences on employee performance among the IT companies employees. The data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) softwareanalysis revealed that workforce diversity, training and development had significantly related with performance of employees.

Key Words: Workforce Diversity, Training and Development, Employee Performance

Introduction:

Employees are major assets of any organization. These unique assets through effective training become imperative in order to maximize the job performance. Also position them to take on the challenges of the today’s competitive business climate. In India, Bangalore is one of the most globally competitive cities; it attracts highly skilled and extremely innovative people to work here. Globalization and Internet have reduced the gap in the time to market scale. Thus hyper competition is almost unavoidable in every field. At the same time the technical challenge of industrial problems is getting more difficult as well as more complex. In Bangalore workforce has employees from different states, cultures, generations and genders. This multiculturalism has positioned for improving organizational performance. It is highly influenced by individual employee performance. Employee’s performance is the behavior and attitude of an employee at work. The accomplishment of the industry depends on its employee performance. Therefore, upper management knows the significance of expense in training for the advantage of improving employee performance and also places them to get the challenges of the today’s competitive business environment. One of the key factors of any organizations is its employees. Employee performance can also be influenced by workforce diversity, training and development of an individual employee. This research investigates the relationship between work force diversity (cultural, age, gender, and ethnicity), training development and employee performance in the work force diversity, training and development influences on employee performance among the employees.

Benefits of Managing Workforce Diversity:

- High level of Productivity
- Exchange of varieties of ideas and Team work
- Learning and growth
- Effective Communication
- Diverse Experience

Need of Training & Development in the Workplace:

- To make employees more effective and productive.
- To match the employee specification with job requirements of organizational needs.
- To cope with the technological advancements.
- To improve the quality of product I service.

- To reduce wastage.
- To minimize industrial accidents.
- To prevent obsolescence.
- To deal with human relations.
- To increase the fair value earning power & job security of employees.
- It moulds the employee's attitude and helps them to achieve a better co-operation.

Effectiveness of Training in the Workplace:

- The productivity of individual on job increases.
- Employee gets job satisfaction at job.
- Psychological problems of employees come to low level.
- Involvement of employees in their jobs increases.
- A sense of commitment and loyalty among employees develop.
- Employees get higher salaries and incentives on production basis.
- Quality and quantity of the total production increase.
- Sales and market shares of the company in the market improves.
- Profit improves and that leads to progress of the business

Statement of the Problem:

An organization requires 6 Ms for its successful functioning they are Men, Machine, Money, Materials Method, and Minutes. Out of all these resources, the primary and crucial resource is men. An Organization consists of people coming from different background that is religion, caste, education, qualification, gender, and birth place etc. This server as major factor towards a communication, interpersonal relationship that in turn influence their organization productivity, Hence with these objective following questions has been identified.

Objective of the Study:

Primary Objectives:

- Workforce Diversity in Preethi Hospitals Of Medical Science & Research Lake Area Madurai

Secondary Objectives:

- To analyse the important of study in workforce diversity
- To analyse the attitude of employee & employer towards workforce diversity
- To provide suitable suggestions for tackling workforce diversity

Need of the Study:

All employees is affected by a lot of internal & external factors in the workplace. Number of employee can perform as an individual there are a lot of situation that demand frequent interaction and communication with is coworkers 'and management. Workforce diversity is a major factor that affects directly and indirectly then points mention above. A study on workforce diversity is needed in all organizations.

Scope of the Study:

- The study throws light on need for workforce diversity procedure and this Study facilitates the management for further improvement on the same.
- This study will be useful when similar kind of research is undertaken.

Hypothesis of the Study:

A research hypothesis is a specific, clear, and testable or predictive statement about the possible outcome of a scientific research study based on a particular property of a population such as presumed different between group on a particular variable or relationship between variable

- Ho; There is no relationship between salary and working experience
- H1; There is relationship between salary and working experience

Research Design:

Descriptive research method has been followed to conduct the research study. Descriptive study is concerned with describing the particular characteristics of Preethi Hospitals of Medical Science & Research so we have to use descriptive research design

Research Methodology:

Research methodology explains the various steps that are generally adopted by the researcher in studying the research problem along with logic behind them

Source of Data:

- Primary Data: Well-structured questionnaire has been used for the collection of primary data from the respondents. The method used is interview schedule.
- Secondary Data: The secondary data was collected from collected from the company records, various magazines, journals, and various web sites

Method of Data Collection:

The sampling unit means the type of sample involved in the research. It inclusively include employee of the Preethi Multispecialty Hospital Pvt Ltd.

Sampling Size:

It refers to the number of items to be selected from the universe to constitute a sample as been suggested by the company 100 sample were considered for the purpose of the study

Analytical Tools for The Study:

- Percentage Analysis Method
- Chi-Square test
- Correlation Analysis

Review of Literature:

Leach, George, Jackson, and Labella (1995) Used the term working with diversity in place of managing diversity. They implied that working with diversity "calls forth the challenge to be curious, inquire, interact, reflect, and experiment. It requires individuals to be respectful, curious, patient, and willing to learn"

According to (Wittenbaum & Stasser, 1996), "These companies developed diversity programs to address the needs of their workers, satisfy the demands of their competitiveness, or fulfil the requirements of their role in the community. It is important to note that these companies were extremely visionary and were some of the first companies to start implementing diversity programs. Similarly, Work believed that while the needs for managing diversity may appear to grow mainly out of notions of social and economic "fairness" and "morality," the clear and central need for effectively managing diversity is maintaining and improving corporate productivity and profitability in national and global competition.

R. M. Wentling, N. Palma-Rivas (1997) The main focus of this report is to describe in detail the literature on diversity in the workforce to bring about an understanding of the complexity and breadth of workplace diversity issues. The report also intends to provide insights on the trends that have emerged in the field of diversity, and information that can be used to develop new and unique approaches that fit the specific needs of particular organizations. To accomplish this, the authors summarized information on workforce diversity issues from research studies, books, reports, journal articles, related magazines newspaper articles on diversity in the workforce.

According to Jackson (1998) These minorities are considered include any person who is not a white-male. Women today, who currently make up less than half the work force, are expected to fill 65 percent of the jobs created during this decade

Research by Gilbert, Stead, and Ivancevich (1999) in empirical research supports the notion that diversity management can have a positive spillover effect in the workplace. Found that women who were hired in organizations that valued diversity were found to be qualified for the job that they held; however, the affirmative action label stigmatized women regardless of job type.

Theoretical Framework:

The following diagram shows that workforce diversity and training and development influences on employee performances. In this study „Workforce Diversity, Training and Development“ is considered as an independent variable whereas dependent variable is Employee Performance“. Study identified the relationship among these variables. On the basis of the results, the conclusion and recommendations are provided.

Conclusion:

Organizations must embrace and understand the importance of diversity in order to remain competitive, respond to globalization and promote innovation and productivity within its organization. Based on the results

showed the overall effects of workforce diversity (culture, age, gender and ethnicity) towards employee performance in an organization is significant in demographic variables in most of the ways. The current study revealed that there is a positive moderate correlation between workforce diversity and employee performance. This study mainly focuses on the influence of training in enhancing the performance of the employees. Training plays vital role in the building of competencies of new as well as current employees to perform their job in an effective way. The main objective of every training session is to increase the value to the performance of the employees; hence all type of businesses design training and development programs of their employees as a continuous activity. Training, education and effective communication will help to execute strong change management practices. It also prepares employees to hold future position in an organization with full capabilities and helps to overcome the deficiencies in any job related area. This study found that the overall effects of training and development (training need, effectiveness and employee training development) having an impact on employee performance in an organization and it is significant in most of the ways. Also this study revealed that there is a positive moderate correlation between training and development and employee performance.

References:

1. Adams, J. S. (1965). Inequality in social exchange. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*,62, 335-343.
2. Aosa, E. (2011). Strategic management within Kenya firms. *DBA Africa Management Review*, (2012). 8(1), 1-21.
3. Baridam, D.M (2002). *Management and Organisation Theory*, 3rd Ed. Sherbrooke Associates. Port Harcourt.
4. Black, M.M. & Holden, E. W. (1998) the impact of gender on productivity and satisfaction among medical school psychologist. *Journal of clinical Psychology in Medical Settings*, March, 117-131.
5. Cohen, kim (1999), Commentary on the organisational sciences special issue on complexity, *Organization science* 10(may-June), 373-376.
6. Denison, D. R. (1990). *Corporate culture and organizational effectiveness*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.